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Unseen scholars: A qualitative inquiry into the research experiences and challenges of SHS students in remote areas

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Abstract

In contemporary times, research and innovation have led to remarkable advancements, significantly influencing progress and shaping the future. This study provides an in-depth analysis of the unique obstacles, experiences, and challenges faced by students as they engage in writing and conducting research. Ten participants were purposively selected for the study, grounded in Social Capital Theory, Digital Divide Theory, and Self-efficacy Theory. A phenomenological research design, along with Colaizzi's data analysis method, was employed to derive the findings.

Data were collected through in-depth, semi-structured, one-on-one interviews and focus group discussions (FGDs). The findings revealed several key themes. Participants described their experiences as transformative, varied, interpersonal, uncertain, and marked by elements of risk and safety. The challenges identified included socioeconomic factors, access to educational resources and technology, safety and well-being, and a lack of engagement and motivation. Notably, differences emerged between senior high school (SHS) students in accessible areas regarding educational opportunities and resources, as well as interest and knowledge.

To cope with these challenges, students employed strategies such as time management, organization, and resourcefulness. The impact of these experiences on their academic and personal growth was significant, fostering expanded worldviews, perseverance, resilience, and enhanced knowledge and skills. The study's findings underscore the need for the education sector to implement targeted interventions that improve students' competencies in research writing and execution.

Keywords: Conducting Research; SHS Research Challenges; Remote Areas; Resource Accessibility

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and Rationale

In the present time, different amazing things have emerged as a product of research and innovation. Research plays a crucial role in driving progress and shaping the future. According to the National Science Board (2018), research has become essential for societal development and economic growth due to continuous advancements in technology and the increasing demand for new solutions. Hassan (2022) emphasizes that research is a critical driver of innovation, enabling the development of new products, services, and technologies that can enhance people's lives and contribute to economic growth. According to the survey conducted by Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2018), 75 percent of the increase in the country's economy around the world was due to research. Those different conducted research by individuals resulted to a certain products, innovations and programs that could help country's economy especially in agriculture, infrastructure, healthcare, technology and of course in education.

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Additionally, as highlighted by Oliver et al. (2014), research contributes to personal and professional development by fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills. These skills are valuable not only in academia but also in the workplace, making research an integral part of societal progress and individual growth. Furthermore, Shen et al. (2021) states that research serves as a catalyst for change, driving advancements in diverse areas such as renewable energy, healthcare technologies, artificial intelligence, and sustainable development. Through systematic inquiry and experimentation, researchers explore innovative solutions to pressing societal challenges, pushing the boundaries of knowledge and technology.

In fact, the continuous pursuit of knowledge through research leads to the discovery of new ideas, solutions, and advancements that benefit the society (Fayomi, Okokpujie, & Udo, 2018). By investing more in research, Moyer, Kordsmeier and Song (2017) stated that research can foster and create a culture of curiosity, creativity, and collaboration. It encourages individuals to question existing norms, explore new possibilities, and work together towards common goals. Through research, individuals can expand their horizons, challenge assumptions, and make meaningful contributions to their respective fields paving the way for future innovations and improvements. That is why, almost all the institutions around the world included research in their curriculum to engage their students to research. And allow them to explore every aspect of life creating something valuable and helpful to everyone. They make research one of the major requirements before a student can proceed to next level of education.

In fact, in the Philippines, the transition from the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum to K-12 Education Curriculum marked a significant shift in the country's educational landscape (Leonores, 2019). This emphasizes a more research-focused approach to learning. This transformation aimed to align the Philippine education system with global standards, enhance the quality of education, and better prepare students for the demands of the 21st century. That's why, Guido and Orleans (2018) states that SHS students will encounter a much more subjects that is research-based focus. Two of these subjects is the Practical Research 1 and 2 in both Grade 11 and Grade 12 students. This means that SHS students are required to conduct and produce research outputs before graduating.

However, according to Peñeda & Caidoy (2023), creating academic research is among the most laborious tasks in academia. It is a crucial academic assignment that motivates students to complete in the present day. It necessitates a keen eye for detail, robust critical thinking skills, and a substantial investment of time and energy. Researchers are tasked with delving deep into a subject, sourcing information from diverse outlets, scrutinizing data, and presenting their discoveries in a logical and organized manner (Thonney & Montgomery, 2019). The research process really unfolds through multiple intricate stages, starting with formulating a research question, progressing to conducting thorough literature reviews, collecting, and analyzing data, and culminating in drawing insightful conclusions. Each phase demands precision and unwavering commitment, rendering the task of writing research a laborious and time-intensive endeavor (Ling et al., 2021).

Additionally, it also requires dedication and time, which can pose a challenge for students due to the multitude of academic obligations they have. As mentioned by Bailey (2019), students face numerous challenges when it comes to conducting research, which can be attributed to various reasons. One major obstacle is the lack of motivation and interest, which can be attributed to traditional methods of learning and a lack of background knowledge about research. This can lead to students struggling with selecting appropriate research topics, often choosing topics that are either too broad or too limited for the given task. That is why there were much research conducted claiming that writing research is a serious and common issue that students experience and should be addressed (Peñeda & Caidoy, 2023).

In the Philippines, Digamon (2023) indicates that students often grapple with recognizing the critical importance of research writing, which can contribute to escalating levels of burnout and stress. According to Bocar (2013), only 33% of the students who has research subjects in SHS successfully finished and met the requirements. The remaining 66% of the SHS students found it difficult to finish their research and failed to comply all the requirements for the subject. This struggle suggests that students may not fully appreciate how integral research writing is to their academic development and success, which can result in increased emotional and psychological strain as they attempt to navigate the demands of their academic workload. With that, many fails to finish and complete the requirements for research. As a result, they failed the subject.

Meanwhile, Masango (2015) suggested that if students are to create excellent research, they must exhibit qualities such as being proactive and having access to resources. Further, the Department of Education (n.d.) commits to providing resources and assistance to SHS students in completing their research requirements. The DepEd provides different learning resources such as gadgets, computers and printed books and even free learning websites where the students can retrieve and get information and data regarding their research topics. However, that assistance to resources were only helpful to those areas that were located in an accessible place especially in the urban areas and some in rural areas

that has internet connectivity and immediate access to transportation (Pablo & Lasaten, 2018). Those SHS students who lived and studies in accessible schools seems to have an easy life and research experience since they all have the access to information and data that they want for their research study. They also have a more knowledgeable research teacher that can easily be tapped or contacted when they need to ask queries and clarification regarding their research topics (Gumarang et.al, 2021). These SHS students has the motivation, interest and the urge to complete certain research since they already have the resources and the guidance that they need.

As a result, Kimson (2017) state that those students who are in urban and accessible areas seems to finish their research studies on time. And encounter no to fewer challenges as they conduct their research. They are the students who has a good experience and create a good research study. This is because they are privilege to have an accessible resource for their data (Opateye & Eyem, 2022). This is due to the fact that they are also blessed with different technological advancements that could helped them in making a good research study. Such as computers, cellphones, and fast internet connectivity. They are those students who do not exert great effort and time in searching for data and information regarding their research. Further, according to Aithal & Kumar (2017), those SHS students who experience no challenges and rich in different research resources seems to excel in higher education and work fields.

On the other hand, however, how about those SHS students living and is situated in remote and disadvantaged areas where there is limited access to learning resources and assistance? Those SHS students who spend more time and effort searching for research data that are helpful for their research study. Those SHS students who sometimes struggle in writing and making their research manuscript since they lack basic research background and do not have access to technology. Those SHS students who lack interest and understanding about research. Can they keep up with those SHS students residing in accessible areas and whose school location is easily visible? Will these Senior High School students excel in higher education and in their respective work fields? Will their challenges and experiences help them become more proficient in the field of research compared to students in accessible areas? Or will these challenges be a reason for them to discontinue their research work and fail in their subjects? Will these challenges and experiences of them be the reason why they don't still understand and know how to make or conduct research? Will these challenges and experiences of them be the hindrance in excelling and continuing to higher education? Are their experiences and challenges the reason behind the current phenomenon experienced by SHS students where they lack the knowledge to conduct research and sometimes struggle in conducting research studies?

If that's the case, how can we help them ease the burden that they are experiencing as well as those challenges that could sometimes hinder their success in making research, especially, those challenges that sometimes affects their interest, academic performance and success? How can the government improve the SHS curriculum to help all SHS students including those in the remote and disadvantage areas master and loved research?

With these questions and gaps, the researcher is encouraged to explore and understand the lived experiences and challenges of SHS students in remote areas as they navigate the process of conducting and writing research as part of their SHS curriculum subjects. This seeks to provide an in-depth understanding of the unique obstacles they face, the strategies they employ to overcome those different barriers and its impact to their academic performance and personal development as individual. By highlighting the voices and experiences these students have, the researcher aimed to shed light on the realities of remote education and research in underserved areas. Further, the researcher aimed to inform the authority for different educational policy and practices as well as the implementation of intervention programs designed to achieve quality of research among SHS students in remote and disadvantage areas.

With that, this research study will be conducted to SHS students who are situated or living in remote or disadvantaged areas of Calbayog City, particularly in Patong-Happy Valley National High School and Seven Hills National School which are both schools in Calbayog City Division who offers SHS Curriculum and is situated in remote and disadvantage areas of the division.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1. Conceptual Literature

It is a commonly held belief that engaging in research is a challenging and often unexciting task for certain students. Even for teachers, this field poses significant difficulties, requiring extensive reading, validation, numerical aptitude, and patience to uncover the most valuable information pertaining to the given topic (Siguan & Ecija, 2020). This is due to the fact that research plays a crucial role in shaping the learning experiences of SHS students, providing them with opportunities to delve deeper into subjects, develop critical thinking skills, and contribute to knowledge creation. According to Smith (2018), research stands as a cornerstone in the academic landscape of SHS students, offering a

gateway to deeper exploration, honing critical thinking prowess, and fostering a culture of intellectual curiosity. Engaging in research not only empowers SHS students to delve into subjects with a critical lens but also cultivates skills in data analysis, problem-solving, and communication, essential for their academic and professional growth (Jones & Lee, 2019). However, the journey of conducting research in SHS is not without its challenges. Students often encounter obstacles that come into their different experiences such as limited access to resources, time constraints, and unfamiliarity with research methodologies, which can hinder their research endeavors (Brown, 2020).

According to Kuper & Huges (2014) as cited by Dziuban et.al. (2020) in their book titled *Conducting Research in Online and Blended Learning Environments*, states that students in remote and inaccessible areas seems to have a varied and transformative experiences as compared to students in accessible areas. This is due to their geographical locations that can significantly influence their educational journey and overall development. Dziuban et.al. (2020) further stated that students in remote and inaccessible areas may develop a different perspective on learning, problem-solving, and life in general. These students are likely to exhibit resilience, adaptability, and creativity in overcoming the obstacles posed by their environment, leading to a transformative educational experience.

This claim was strengthened by Thompson & Palmer (2022) that revealed on their book titled *Conducting Undergraduate Research in Education: A Guide for Students in Teacher Education Programs*, that students in accessible areas may have easier access to educational resources, technology, and opportunities. While this can be advantageous in many ways, it may also limit their exposure to diverse perspectives and challenges that students in remote areas encounter. As a result, their educational experiences may be more standardized and less transformative as compared to their counterparts in remote areas.

Meanwhile, Felbab (2014) states in his blog that being a researcher living in an inaccessible and remote areas like in Negros, Philippines is difficult, dangerous and vulnerable in context. This is due to challenges that stem from the unique geographical, social, and environmental conditions prevalent in such areas, impacting the well-being and safety of researchers. Like for example, the inaccessibility to basic infrastructure, such as roads, electricity, and communication networks, impedes the smooth conduct of research activities. Researchers may face difficulties in transporting equipment, accessing essential supplies, and communicating with the outside world. Further, remote and inaccessible areas are often characterized by security concerns that pose serious risks to researchers. These areas may be prone to criminal activities, insurgency, or natural disasters, exposing researchers to potential dangers (Katz & Coleman, 2014). Additionally, researchers may find themselves at the mercy of unpredictable environmental hazards, further exacerbating the risks they face on a daily basis.

That is why, as mentioned by Planning (2016) in the book titled *Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*, SHS students living in inaccessible areas turns to have a negative attitude towards research. This is due to different internal and external factors that affects their motivation, interest and engagement to do the process. This includes communication barriers, including poor network coverage and transportation limitations and lack of guidance and encouragement from teachers, parents, or mentors in navigating the research process leaving students feeling overwhelmed and ill-equipped to embark on research endeavors. The claim was also proven by Rojas (2020), that states that students experienced anxiety and emotional breakdown regarding the different factors that could hamper the conduct of their research. He further argues that, students' heightened anxiety levels can lead to a diminished optimism towards research and a perception of research as less beneficial, and vice versa. Students expressed feeling anxious because of their struggles to grasp the fundamentals and significance of research, along with its challenging and intricate nature.

But, regardless of these Rubin & Babbie (2011) mentioned on the 8th edition of the book titled *Research Methods for Social Work*, that those students in far flung areas who experienced stress and anxiety in their studies and while conducting a research projects or any other school activities seems to develop and create a unique coping strategies and mechanisms that would help them turn themselves and views into a more resilient way. They further argue that those students who are privilege with different resources that they need in their studies and research projects or activities such as technologies, books, internet connectivity and other learning resources turns to be weak and not resilient. They are those students who can be easily affected by stress and anxiety.

2.2. Research/Theoretical Literature

Students engaging in research projects undergo a transformative journey marked by challenges, growth, and discovery. The lived experiences of students as they conduct research encompass a diverse range of emotions, obstacles, and achievements that shape their academic and personal development. From formulating research questions to presenting findings, students navigate a complex process that fosters critical thinking, creativity, and perseverance (Reisel et.al.,

2015). As they embark on their journey of conducting research, their experiences become vital in shaping their understanding, engagement, and growth (Thomas & Busby, 2003). These live experiences not only contribute to the academic prestige of their institutions but also have the potential to generate new knowledge that can be applied to address real-world problems and contribute to the betterment of society (Nenty, 2009).

Qasem and Zayyad (2019) highlighted that students face several challenges when conducting research. Some may have internal constraints, such as motivation, while others may have external constraints, such as understanding research methodology, financial restrictions, and lack of resources. These challenges resulted to their experiences as they undergo the process of writing and conducting research. This claim was agreed upon by Lestari (2020) on his study titled an analysis of students' difficulties in writing undergraduate thesis at English education program of Muhammadiyah University of Bengkulu that revealed that students come with different experiences starting from Intellectual experiences, emotional experiences, social experiences, and physical experiences. He further stated that those students who are currently conducting research have more experiences in their intellectual and physical realms as compared to their emotional and social experiences. This is because there physical and intellectual aspects play a crucial role in their success in research.

Further, according to the conducted study of Peterson & McNamee (2020), they revealed that 55% or 110 out of 200 native and tribal student respondent-participants in Ohio Middle School who engaged in conducting research often prioritize their intellectual and physical pursuits at the expense of their emotional and social experiences. This is because the nature of research fosters an environment rich in intellectual engagement, driving students to immerse themselves in academic pursuits. In which the academic environment also places a significant emphasis on intellectual achievements, leading students to prioritize their academic goals over social and emotional well-being. Further, research projects may involve physical activities such as laboratory work or field experiments, these physical demands are often intertwined with intellectual pursuits. Students may perceive physical activities within the research context as means to achieve intellectual goals rather than opportunities for physical experiences (Weiderhold, 2015). As a result, the emphasis remains on intellectual engagement, with physical experiences serving as a means to an end rather than ends in themselves.

However, Sithole (2016) on her study titled conducting research for the first time: Experiences of under-graduate social work students, stated that students who conduct research for the first time have an extraordinary research experience in terms of there emotional and social aspects. These students tend to have more exciting experience emotionally and socially. She revealed that 67% of the graduating social work students who conducted thesis for the first time seems to intensely experience situations that is in connection to their emotional and social aspects. Which in turn has an impact to the success of their research. She further revealed that those students who experience situations emotionally and socially tend to develop a sense of resiliency and will easily cope up to different challenges in their next research endeavor.

But, on the study of Haleem & Asghar (2023) titled problems experienced by undergraduate students in conducting research in online distance learning they argued that intellectual experiences, emotional experiences, physical experiences, and social experiences were equal and are connected from each other. They stated that these four experiences commonly encountered by students while conducting research has a big impact not only to the success of their research works but also to their selves and personal growth. They explained that if a student-researcher has an extraordinary experienced emotionally, it also has an effect to his/her physical, intellectual and social aspects.

Meanwhile, Alsied & Ibrahim (2017), argues that high school students living in urban areas seems to have a good research experience and excel better in college education rather than those high school students who are living in remote areas and are far from school where they are currently studying. They found out that those high school students who were living in urban areas and cities often have better research experiences since they have access to resources such as libraries, research facilities, and technology. They may also have more opportunities for mentorship and collaboration with professionals in their field. Additionally, students in urban areas may benefit from a more diverse and vibrant academic community, which can enrich their research experience (Ibrahim, 2023). On the other hand, however, students in remote and disadvantaged areas have an unpleasant experience since they face various challenges when conducting research (Taskeen et.al.,2014).

However, according to Garcia et. al. (2020), students in disadvantaged areas often face a myriad of socio-economic challenges, including limited access to resources, inadequate infrastructure, and lack of academic support. Despite these obstacles, these students exhibit remarkable resilience and determination in pursuing their research goals. Which in turn, they will become successful in their research. And excel further when they reach higher education and even in the field of work life.

With the different experiences encountered by the students as they conduct research, Nareem (2022) states that these experiences are associated with different challenges. She states that research students face difficulties in choosing a research topic, honing their study focus, gaining familiarity with information resources, refining their online search abilities, improving their data analysis proficiency, and managing their time effectively. Further, she also revealed that student-researcher found it challenging to write research manuscripts in English especially those students whose first language is not English.

Additionally, Siguan & Ecija (2020) on their study titled Challenges encountered by senior high school students' researchers in Salcedo 1 District revealed that senior high school student-researchers identified 20 challenges, with 75% of them indicating significant difficulty related to financial constraints in meeting research requirements. The funds they intend to allocate are primarily designated for internet usage and printing documents essential for timely submission with high levels of validity and reliability. This further means that, students expressed concerns about the costs associated with accessing necessary resources, such as academic journals, online databases, and research materials including internet connectivity load and data usage. Additionally, the funds needed for printing documents, including research papers, surveys, and data collection instruments, also contributed to their financial burden. Furthermore, the students also emphasized the importance of timely submission and the need for their research outputs to meet high standards of validity and reliability. However, limited financial resources presented challenges in fulfilling these requirements.

Moreover, as added by Guido & Orleans (2020) on their study titled Investigating challenges and barriers encountered by senior high school students in the conduct of research, they revealed that students face numerous challenges and obstacles, including struggles with grammar construction and language proficiency, time management issues, confusion regarding statistical analysis, and a lack of motivation to continue their research. Additionally, they further stated that balancing household responsibilities poses a significant barrier to conducting research across all Senior High School (SHS) strands.

For Leonares (2019) implies in his study that research students faced the following challenges: 1) Limited basic research knowledge from Junior High School, 2) Topic formulation, 3) Collaboration within a research team, 4) Limited resources, 5) Data analysis and interpretation, and 6) Maintaining motivation throughout the study. Further, time management was also crucial for completing the study as research subjects were taught alongside specialized and applied subjects, which often required term papers and reports due for submission at the same time. In this sense, the study underscored the importance of incorporating fundamental research lessons during the junior high school years, particularly targeting grades 9 and 10. It also highlighted the necessity for Time Management Seminars for Senior High School students to assist them in adapting to the increased requirements of the program that readies them for tertiary education. Additionally, a collaborative work plan involving SHS teachers teaching applied and specialized subjects could be developed and implemented to accommodate students' performance schedules and submission deadlines (Ajodhia-Andrews, 2016).

In this regard, Burnette et. al. (2014) recommended in his study that the government should provide and help the students in terms of grants, scholarship programs and providing readily accessible tool to be used by the students. This include but not limited to free access to online journals and research databases, free internet connectivity among schools, tablets, computers and printers and of course printed books in any fields and subjects. In this way, students will not anymore think of the burden brought about by financial instability and other factors and challenges.

These cited study and research work served as a guide for the researcher in devising his own study. This mentioned study gave the researcher a better understanding of the investigations and helped him chose the most appropriate research methodology.

2.3. Framework of the Study

This serves as the theoretical foundation that guides the research process, providing a structured approach to inquiry and analysis. It establishes the context, scope, and direction of the study, outlining the theoretical perspectives, concepts, and variables that shape the research design. By delineating the framework, this can elucidate the relationships between different elements of the study, set the boundaries of investigation, and establish a coherent framework for interpreting and analyzing data. This framework not only informs the research methodology and data collection but also offers a lens through which findings are interpreted and conclusions are drawn.

4.1.1 Theoretical Framework

This study drew upon Social Capital Theory to provide a valuable framework for understanding and analyzing the research experiences and challenges of SHS students in remote areas. According to Portes (1998), Social Capital Theory emphasizes the significance of social networks and connections in individuals' lives. In the context of this study, the theory can shed light on how the social capital of SHS students in remote areas influences their research experiences. By examining the role of mentors, peers, teachers, and community members, researchers can explore the extent to which these social networks provide support, guidance, and access to resources for conducting research (Coleman, 1988). The theory assumes and emphasizes the significance of having strong social ties to gain access to valuable resources. This idea can be looked at in terms of how the friendships and networks of SHS students in remote and disadvantage areas impact their ability to get different kinds of facilities and resources, technology, funding, connection with academic institutions, knowledgeable and helpful individuals and access to other resources that is crucial for their research endeavors (Warschauer, 2003).

Moreover, Social Capital Theory highlights the importance of teamwork and cooperation in research experiences. This is because, as mentioned by Kenton (2022), social capital allows a group of people to work together effectively to achieve a common purpose or goal. It allows a society or organization, such as a corporation or a nonprofit, to function together as a whole through trust and shared identity, norms, values, and mutual relationships. With that, the theory can be used to explore how SHS students in remote areas engage in knowledge sharing, collaboration, and collective problem-solving within their social networks to finished their research works despite of the locations they are situated in. (van Dijk, 2006).

Also, this study followed the Digital Divide Theory. It is a theory that describes the gap between people who have access to affordable, reliable internet service (and the skills and gadgets necessary to take advantage of that access) and those who lack it (Taylor, 2024). As mentioned by Castelle (2003) on his book titled "The Information Age: Economy, Society, and Culture" he highlighted that the theory helps specify information in investigating how limited access to technology, such as digital devices and reliable internet connectivity, hinders the ability of the SHS students in remote and disadvantage areas while they conduct their research, access information, and collaborate with peers and mentors.

Also, Digital Divide Theory, argues that the isolation of students in remote areas from research opportunities, workshops, and experts in the field limits their exposure to the benefits and significance of research. Without access to these enriching experiences, students may struggle to grasp the relevance of research in their academic pursuits and future endeavors, fostering a sense of detachment and skepticism towards research practices.

Moreover, the study was also drawn upon Self-efficacy theory proposed by Albert Bandura. This is a theory that focuses on an individual's belief in their own capabilities to accomplish tasks, achieve goals, and overcome challenges. According to Bandura (1977), self-efficacy plays a critical role in motivation, behavior, and personal development. It is shaped by four primary sources of information. First, mastery experiences, where past successes enhance self-efficacy while failures diminish it. Second, vicarious experiences, where observing others succeed or fail influences one's belief in their own capabilities. Third, social persuasion, where verbal encouragement and feedback from others can boost or lower self-efficacy. Finally, emotional and physiological states, where positive emotions and a sense of calm enhance self-efficacy, while anxiety or stress can undermine it. Individuals with higher self-efficacy are more likely to set challenging goals, exert effort, persevere in the face of obstacles, and achieve positive outcomes.

With this, the research study is being anchored to this theory since the theory offers a perspective to understand the research experiences of Senior High School (SHS) students in remote and disadvantaged areas. It suggests that a person's belief in their ability to complete tasks greatly impacts their actions, motivation, and achievements. By analyzing the real-life experiences of these students, self-efficacy theory provides a valuable framework for comprehending their research pursuits. This actually illuminates the motivational dynamics at play: students with high self-efficacy are more inclined to persist in their research efforts despite encountering obstacles, while those with lower self-efficacy may falter in the face of challenges.

Another, the study also followed the Place-based Education Theory. According to Yemini, Engel and Simon (2023), Place-based Education Theory is an educational method that highlights the link between learning and the physical environment where teachers and students interact. This approach integrates the significance and experiences of the surroundings into teaching and learning, often transcending the confines of traditional classroom settings. This leverages geographical surroundings to facilitate genuine, significant, and captivating personalized learning for students. In particular, it is described as an immersive learning experience by the Center for Place-Based Learning and Community Engagement (Ark, n.d.). This approach involves immersing students in the local heritage, cultures,

landscapes, opportunities, and experiences, which then serve as a basis for studying various subjects like language arts, mathematics, social studies, science, and more throughout the curriculum.

4.1.2 Conceptual Framework

Students embarking on conducting and making research experience a transformative process characterized by hurdles, development, and exploration. Their real-life encounters during research entail various emotions, challenges, and successes, influencing both their academic and personal growth especially those SHS students who lived, and their school location is in remote and disadvantage areas. With that, they are unfortunate and were not blessed with various resources such as cellphones, stable internet connectivity, books and etc. Unlike those SHS students who is living in urban and accessible areas, they were blessed with different research resources that could help them in conducting their research.

This study determined the lived experiences of SHS students in remote and disadvantaged areas. Figure 1 depicts the flow of the study as well as the interplay of the different variables that were considered during the investigation. The first and the topmost frame showed the general problem of the study. This pertains to the Lived experiences of the SHS students who are living in the remote and disadvantaged areas and whose school location is difficult to access, while they conduct their research. The second and third frames showed the independent variables, these are the Experiences as well as the challenges encountered by this SHS students as they conduct their research. And these variables were connected by two-headed arrows representing a two directional relationship between them.

The fourth frame showed the coping mechanism and strategies employed by the SHS students in remote and disadvantage areas as they face their challenges and unique experiences while conducting their research. And it is connected by a single-headed arrow that shows its relationship between the second frame (experiences) and third frame (challenges).

The fifth frame represented the impact to their academic and personal growth. This was being connected also by a two single-headed arrow showing its relationship to the experiences and challenges. This can be further interpreted that by knowing first the experiences and the challenges of this SHS students they can examine the impact of it to themselves.

Lastly, the last frame showed the output of the study which is the proposed program and intervention.

Figure 1 The Paradigm of the study showing the Lived Experiences of SHS Students in Remote and Disadvantage Areas as they conduct their Research

2.4. Research Problem

This qualitative study explored and understood the lived experiences as well as the challenges faced by SHS students in remote areas as they navigate into the process of conducting research as part of their SHS Curriculum.

- Specifically, this sought answers to the following questions;
- What are the experiences of the SHS students in remote areas while conducting research?
- What are the specific challenges encountered by SHS students in remote areas as they conduct their research?
- How do these challenges differ from those faced by students in more accessible locations?
- What are the strategies and coping approaches employed by SHS students in remote areas to overcome the challenges they had while conducting research?
- How do these experiences and challenges encountered by SHS students in remote areas as they conduct their research impact their academic and personal growth?

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The study employed and adopted the phenomenological method of qualitative research. This research design was used to explore and investigate the lived experiences as well as the challenges of SHS students in remote and disadvantage areas of the school's division of Calbayog City as they navigate the process of conducting research as part of their SHS curriculum. Including also their coping mechanism and the impacts of these challenges to their personal and academic growth. Since it is evident nowadays that there is a big gap between the SHS students living in accessible areas as compared to SHS students living in remote and disadvantage areas in terms of their ability and interest in conducting research. Through this phenomenological research design, a descriptive analysis of the experiences and the challenges of the SHS students in remote and disadvantaged areas was created.

In fact, Phenomenology according to Delve and Limpaecher (2022), is a qualitative approach aimed at comprehending and describing the fundamental essence of a phenomenon. It focuses on investigating the everyday experiences of individuals, setting aside any preconceived assumptions held by the researchers. In essence, it delves into the lived experiences of people to gain deeper insights into their understanding and interpretation of those experiences. This approach allows for a richer understanding of the universal nature of the phenomenon under study. Further, as mentioned by Bliss (2016), it is a philosophical approach that focuses on the study of subjective experiences and the way individuals perceive and interpret the world. It explores the first-person perspective and aim to understand the essence of human consciousness and the structures of lived experiences.

Phenomenological research study design also places great emphasis on the direct description and analysis of phenomena, without the influence of assumptions or preconceived notions. It was also deemed more convenient to use this approach to explain how people experience a certain phenomenon as this approach explores distinct consciousness structures as they are perceived in the first person. Moreover, as a phenomenological study, it is vital to consider the importance of a phenomenological method. Specifically, in this research study, the Colaizzi method will be utilized to reveal emergent themes and their interwoven relationships. By using this descriptive phenomenological approach, it will give a clear and logical process through which the fundamental structure of an experience can be explored. As it is an experience of or about some object, the intentionality, or being oriented toward something, is the main structural component of an experience.

3.2. Sample of the Study

A total of ten (10) research participants were chosen. The participants of the study were identified senior high school learners who is living in the remote and disadvantaged areas of Calbayog City and whose school location is in inaccessible part of Calbayog City. The target participants were from Grade 11 and 12 students who are currently enrolled in Practical Research 1 and 2 subjects in the SHS regardless of their SHS strand and track, their age and gender.

The selection of participants was made using a purposive sampling technique, guided by specific criteria established by the researchers. Purposive sampling is a nonrandom approach that does not require underlying theories or a predetermined number of participants (Etikan & Alkassim, 2016). This technique is commonly employed in qualitative research to identify and select cases that provide the most informative insights, optimizing the use of available resources. It involves identifying and choosing individuals or groups who possess expertise and knowledge related to the phenomenon of interest.

3.3. Measures

To collect the needed data, the researcher conducted an in-depth one-on-one, face-to-face interview with the participants using a semi-structured interview questions which was being asked by the researcher through a recorded conversation. In order to explore the lived experiences of SHS students in remote and disadvantaged areas including their challenges, coping mechanism, strategies employed and the impact of it to their personal and academic growth while conducting their research. The participants were allowed to speak on to their comfortable language to convey clearly what are their ideas and their intended messages. Then, after the one-on-one, face-to-face interview the researcher validate the data collected through a FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION (FGD) in order to fully understand it and screen down unnecessary data.

Before the conduct of the interview and the FGD, the researcher went to the areas and selected ten (10) participants. Five (5) Grade 11 participants and another five (5) Grade 12 participants. During the conduct of the one-on-one, face-to-face interview; the participants were interviewed separately to achieved a reliable data and avoid the influence of their individual answers. Then, after the interview the FGD was followed. In the FGD, two sessions were made. In the first FGD session, the students were group according to their Grade levels. All Grade 11 students were group together and undergo to the FGD. Same with the Grade 12 students. And, after the first FGD session, this was followed again by the second FGD session. On the second FGD session, they were group randomly regardless of their Grade level and were asked same questions.

Further, the researcher cited explanations about the rationale and the purpose of the study. A general instruction were also enumerated in the introduction phase of the interview and FGD sessions to make the process seamless. The interview guide for the one-on-one, face-to-face interview and on the FGD sessions was researcher-made and that would help the participants analyze and assess their response to each on the questions. For this study to gather the needed data, the use of data saturation is integrated. It is when there is enough information to replicate the study when the ability to obtain additional new information has been attained, and when further coding is no longer feasible.

Also, the semi-structured interview and FGD guide questions went through validation procedure to examine thoroughly the interview questions constructed. And to ensure the accuracy and validity of the instruments to gather necessary information to the study, an intercoder validation was utilized. According to Richards (2009), intercode reliability ensures that the researcher reliably interpreting a code in the same way across time, or that you can rely on your colleagues to use it in the same way. An intercoder validation was employed to enhance the accuracy and validity of the data collected through the interview and FGD guide. This validation procedure aimed to ensure that the interview questions constructed were appropriately designed and that the gathered information could be relied upon for the study's analysis. With this, it was submitted to three researchers from Christ the King College, Calbayog City to see whether or not they agreed to this study's data consistency and validity. By employing the intercoder validation process, the study aimed to enhance the rigor and trustworthiness of its findings. This approach helps minimize biases, errors and inconsistencies that could arise from individual coder interpretations, ultimately leading to more credible research outcomes.

3.4. Procedures

Before the conduct of the study, the researcher sought approval from the Office of the School's Division Superintendent, Department of Education (DepEd) Schools Division of Calbayog City to conduct the study. The researcher also requested permission from the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor to which District the schools was located. After it was approved, the researcher wrote a letter to the principal or school head informing him/her of the approved letter of the conduct of the study and his intention to interview students and collect data from them.

Then, the researcher conducted an in-depth one-on-one, face-to-face interview as well FGD through a recorded conversation with the participants. Measure was employed to abide the ethical principles in the conduct of the research study. Specifically, the participants were reminded and informed about the nature of the study to ensure freedom and to established rapport to provide an avenue for the participants to voluntarily consent or decline participation on the study. The informed consent of each of the participants was also secured. The participants were given enough time to answer the questions and allowed to ask clarifications to the researcher.

During the one-on-one, face-to-face interview with the participants, they are separated and didn't allow to see each other just to avoid bias and influenced their response. Then, it was followed by FGD wherein they were group and asked same questions. After that, the answers of the participants in both one-on-one, face-to-face interview and the FGD are gathered and sealed for transcription and will be shown to an expert for interceding analysis and interpretation. In this

part, data saturation was also employed as when there is enough information to replicate the study when the ability to obtain additional new information has been attained, and when further coding is no longer feasible.

3.5. Data Processing

The researcher employed the Colaizzi method as it allows the researcher to reveal themes and their interwoven relationship that could contribute greatly to the finding of the study. Colaizzi method uncovers genuine live experiences of the participants of this study, thus understanding of the data and identifying significant statements were gathered.

This study follows the 7 stages of the Colaizzi method namely; (1) the reading and re-reading of the transcript, (2) extracting significant statements that pertains to the phenomenon, (3) giving meanings to the statements, (4) repeating steps 1-3, then the researcher can now begin formulating themes, (5) compile an exhaustive description of everything generated in steps 1-4, (6) summarizing the exhaustive description from stage 6, (7) the credibility and the results of the data should be discussed to the participants of the study.

3.6. Ethical Considerations

When conducting research on the lived experiences and challenges faced by Senior High School (SHS) students in remote areas as they navigate the process of conducting research as part of their SHS curriculum, it is essential to adhere to rigorous ethical standards to protect the participants' rights and well-being.

Firstly, informed consent will be obtained from all participants, ensuring they are fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. For participants under the age of 18, parental or guardian consent will also be required. Confidentiality and anonymity will be strictly maintained by anonymizing personal identifiers and securely storing data to prevent unauthorized access. Participants will be informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without any negative consequences, ensuring that their decision does not affect their academic standing or other aspects of their lives.

The study was designed to minimize any potential harm, with sensitive topics approached with care and support provided to participants throughout the process. If necessary, referrals to counseling or other support services will be made available. Cultural sensitivity and respect will guide the research, honoring local customs, traditions, and languages of the remote areas involved in the study. The principle of beneficence will be upheld, balancing the potential benefits of the research, such as improved understanding and support for SHS students in remote areas, against any risks of harm.

Transparency and honesty will be maintained throughout the research process, with participants given access to the study results and any conflicts of interest disclosed. By adhering to these ethical principles, the research aims to protect the rights and well-being of the SHS students participating in the study, ensuring their experiences are documented and understood in a respectful and ethically responsible manner.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Experiences of the SHS students in remote and disadvantaged areas

The educational experience of SHS students in remote and disadvantaged areas is unique and often challenging. These students face various obstacles that impact their learning journey (Rahmayati, Parnell & Himmayani, 2017). In fact, conducting a research study as part of their SHS curriculum is one of the many challenges that SHS students need to experience and overcome. This is because writing and conducting research is one of the most laborious and tedious tasks of every student (Peñeda & Caidoy, 2023). With this scenario, it is necessary to determine the lived experiences of the SHS students living in remote and disadvantage areas as they conduct their research which is part of their SHS curriculum. Among the themes that emerge from the responses of the participants were (1) Experiences are transformative and varied; (2) Experiences are interpersonal; (3) Experiences were uncertain; (4) Experiences possess some risk and safety.

4.1.3 Theme 1: Experiences are Transformative and Varied.

Based from the study, majority of the participants responded that they experienced different kinds of situations or scenarios along the process of writing and conducting research. It was highlighted during the one-on-one, face-to-face interview and FGD sessions that this experiences ranges from simple to difficult, relax to adventurous one. Further, the

participants agreed that the experiences they have experienced in the entire process of writing and conducting research comes with the experiences in the data collection, mobility and transportation, and relationships among people.

For their experiences in terms of data collection, majority of the participants agreed that they have an extraordinary experience in which they needed to double their efforts and time in searching for an information as well as data for their research study. They further agreed that these experiences put them in a way that sometimes their life is at risk.

“Kami sir masaka kami sa igbaw san buntay sir... danay sir masaka kami sa atop san amon balay... para la makabiling ahmm... kanan diri nawawara nga signal san internet sir...”

(we tend to climb sir at the top of the hill...and sometimes we went at the rooftop of our house... just to find for ahmm... stable internet connectivity...)

Moreover, they also highlighted that their experiences when it comes to mobility and transportation is very difficult. This is due to their geographical locations and other external factors that limit their access.

“Opo sir... ahm... sunod lat namon na experience sir... kay ahm ma byahe kami sin halaba na oras tikang didi sa amon barangay ngadto sa Calbayog City para la maka kuha information sa City Library. Tapos mayda pa gud san time sir na danay nakukuan an amon ginsasakyan na habal-habal kay damo luho ngan lubak na mga agian.”

(Yes sir... ahm... another experience we had sir... is ahm we travel long hours from our place to Calbayog City just to access information from the City library. And there were also times that the Habal-habal that we were riding on nearly fell into an accident since there were potholes along the way.)

Further, the participants also encounter rough experiences when it comes to establishing good relationships with other people. For them, it is really important to established some relationships with other people so that when they needed help for their research study there were people who can provide and give help to them. However, there experiences in establishing relationship with people is not that easy. They encounter unpleasant experiences which could sometimes affect their motivation as well as their mental health.

“Ah... mayda ak usa na experience nga... gin isgan ak sir san amon paryente sir... kay... ahm an libro nga akon ginhuram kay narubat san tubig sir... tungod ahmm... tumabok kami sa salog sir pauli namon sa balay sadto...”

(Ah... there is this experience of mine that... I was scolded sir by our relative sir... because... ahm the books that I borrowed was destroyed by water sir...since ahmm... we cross the river sir in going home...)

However, these experiences that they have had the power to brought about significant changes, growth, and development in their lives. In fact, as mentioned by Ventura, Salanova and Llorens (2015), different experiences, whether positive or negative, have the potential to shape one's perspectives, beliefs, behaviors, and overall outlook on life. Through these various experiences this SHS students have as they write and conduct their research study, they can learn valuable lessons, gain new insights, and acquire skills that contribute to personal growth and self-discovery. These transformative experiences can actually lead to shifts in mindset, increased self-awareness, and the development of resilience and adaptability in the face of challenges.

“Pero sir ahmm... an amon mga na experience yana paghimo namon san amon research nga usa na requirements para maka proceed kami ngadto Grade 12 or college... kuan sir... ahmm baga siya may-ada ahmm power para bag-ohon an amon mga pananaw sa kinabuhi... siguro ini nga mga experiences namon... makabulig sa amon na upayon pa an ahmmmm... amon pag-aram panano an paghimo research nga maupay ngan... ahm para magdati kami sir diri la sa research pati liwat sa amon pag-aram...”

(But sir ahmm... these experiences of ours in making research as part of our requirements before proceeding to Grade 12 or in college... ahmmmm has actually ahmm power to change our perspective in life... maybe these experiences of ours... helps us improved ahmmmm... our studies especially in making and conducting research... and so that we will be more knowledgeable not only in making research but also in our overall studies...)

4.1.4 Theme 2: Experiences are Interpersonal.

During the entire process of writing and conducting research, the participants experience different level of emotions that is being resulted from their interactions, relationships and connections from other individuals whom they asked

for any kind of help to finish their research, whether it is personal, social or professional in settings. And majority of this experiences are interpersonal. According to van Wyk (2021), interpersonal experiences refers to the interactions, relationships, and connections we have with other individuals.

“Danay sir gin tetry namon kun mahimo na maka established kami maupay na relasyon ngan pakitungo sa iba nga tawo... ahm amon gin try na hampangon an sangkay ni papa na taga Calbayog nga... ahm kun pwede ba kami makikaturug sa ira balay para mahuman namon an amon ginhihimo na review of related literature and studies...ngan san tumugot na siya san amon request naka feel kami iba iba na emosyon ngan kalipay...”

(Sometimes sir we somewhat established good relationship and interactions with other people... ahm we try to ask the friend of my father in the city that... ahm if we can spend our night in there house so that we can finish our review of related literature and studies... and ahm when he approved our requests we felt different emotions of happiness...)

Moreover, due to their geographical locations, the participants doubled their effort in establishing good interactions and relationships with other people whom they can ask for help. But sometimes, these individuals allowed the participants to experience a negative relationship and interactions.

“Asya adto sir nga experience liwat na gin isgan ak san akon uncle san naghuram ak libro san iya anak na babaye... na feel ko sir na napaawod ak didto san atubang san iba na tawo sir... iya ak ginsingnan nga... kay nano nga mangusog pa kuno kami paghimo sin research nga sa kamatuoran... sa katapusan magin pobre manla gihap ako... tungod kay an akon pamilya wara kapas na paskwelahan ak sa college...”

(This is when I was scolded by my uncle as I borrow the books of his daughter... I felt I was embarrassed in front of the other people sir... he said to me that... why would I exert effort in doing research which in fact... I will still end poor... since my family can't send me to school after college.)

“Usa na experience sir san paghuram... kay danay... ahm nakaka kuha kami mga istorya nga maglain ngan diri mao sir... tikang san tawo na amon ginhuraman... parehas san... “Kalamre, kamo na liwat? Alayon ak pagbalik sadto na kalamrehan na mga libro san una... kun diri niyo adto mabalik... tiwas kam sa akon...”

(Another experience sir with borrowing... is that sometimes... ahm we receive words that are not good sir... from the person whom we borrowed the books sir... like... “Fuck, you again? Kindly return those fucking books you borrowed last time... if you won't return it... you will suffer from my conditions.)

With these negative interpersonal relationships they experience from others, they tend to develop and improved themselves. These interactions with others can have a profound impact on how they perceive the world, their own self, and those around them. Through interpersonal experiences, they learn and develop empathy, communication skills, and social awareness, as they navigate the complexities of human relationships and dynamics (Manjula, 2016). These experiences can range from positive interactions that foster trust, collaboration, and support, to challenging encounters that require conflict resolution, negotiation, and understanding.

Moreover, interpersonal experiences can also contribute to their sense of belonging, identity formation, and emotional well-being. The quality of their relationships, the feedback they receive from others, and the level of social support they have can all influence how they interpret and respond to different situations.

“San ginbalik ko an libro, kahuna ko man na okey na kay aunte... kaso tigda la siya nangisog... tungod kay an libro kay sa iya anak ngan nadiri siya nga ipahuram an libro san iya anak... Pero diri naman ak sana apektado sir... ahmm kay na immune naak sana na mga negatibo na mga pakikitungo sa amon san mga tawo na amon ginaaruan bulig para san amon research... kay tungod ahmm... adlaw adlaw nala sir... or everytime na maghimo ngan magkiwa kami para san amon research...nahibaro nala kami sir labi na ako nga diri nala pansinon iton kay kun aasahan... ahmm mahingadto pa iton san samok...”

(...as I returned the book, I thought it's okey with my aunt... but he gets angry... since those books was owned by her child. she don't want to lend books to others... But I was not affected emotionally sir... ahmm because I am immune with those negative interactions and relationships that they gave to us by these people whom we ask for help in our research... this is because ahmm... it's always everyday sir we experience it... we already learn it sir especially myself that I will just ignore it because if we don't this will create troubles and misunderstandings.)

4.1.3. Theme 3: Uncertain Experiences

Since writing and conducting research is a tedious and laborious task for students. Majority of the participants agreed during the FGD sessions that their experiences is uncertain. They do not have an idea what experiences they might experience along the way. There were times that some unexpected situations come along the way.

“Kuan sir... siguro an amon experiences is common pero diak maaram sir kun nano an mga amon maeexperience along the way... Kay ahmm... sir one-time sadto san mag interview kami san amon participants ngadto sa sunod na barangay... tapos akon tatay gin yaknan na kami na safe amon aagian... kaso along the way san amon paglakat... ahmm mayda man kuno iton umagi na duha na sawa sir... hahaha... akon kuyap sadto sir... kay dagko pa gud...”

(Ahmm sir... maybe our experiences is common but I don't know sir if what kind of experiences we encounter along the way... This is because ahmm... one time sir when we will try to interview our identified participants in the next barangay... so may father already anticipated that we have a safe way going there... however along the way while we are walking... we suddenly encounter two large snake sir... I was nervous at that time sir... since the two snakes were big...)

These uncertain experiences the participants encountered highlights the unique challenges and obstacles they must surpassed as they engage in research activities. This is because, these experiences can evoke feelings of unease, anxiety, or confusion as individuals navigate through unfamiliar or ambiguous circumstances (Sitompul & Anditasari, 2022). However, navigating in these uncertain experiences help developed resilience, adaptability, and the ability to tolerate ambiguity which is an important characteristic that must be developed by these SHS student-participants who are conducting and writing research.

4.1.4 Theme 4: Risk and Safety

Along the process of writing and conducting research everyone cannot avoid encountering those kinds of experiences that possess risk to their safety especially if they are situated or living in far flung areas or remote areas. Majority of the participants responded during the one-on-one, face-to-face interview and FGD sessions that they experienced situations that might put their safety at risk.

“San tipakadto ak sir... nahulog ak san akon ginsasakyan na habal-habal tungod kay ini na habal-habal umagi sa lubak ngan luho na kalsada. Ngan an malungkot pa na part sir kay napiangan ak sir.”

(...while I'm on my way... I fell in the habal-habal since the habal-habal passed to a pothole. And the sad part is I was had an injury and got hurt.)

“Nahibalindas ak sa igbaw san buntay habang namimiling kami signal... tapos sana nahipusdak akon bubot sa tuna sir... ngan an makatarawa sana is... ahmmm... akon mga classmates ira laak gin taw'an.”

(I slipped at the hill top while searching for the stable connection... and my buttocks hit hard to the ground... and the funny thing is... ahmmm... my classmates only laugh at me...)

“...Kami, permi kami napakadto sa Calbayog City para makakuha mga impormasyon... labi na gud sa amon RRL nga part. Bisan pa makusog an uran ngan an mga kalsada ngan agian kay delikado tungod san makusog na uran... pero mag apras gudla kami pakadto... para gud mahuman la namon an research sa tama oras.”

(...we always travel going to Calbayog City just to gather information... especially in our RRL part. Even if the rain is heavy and the road is too dangerous due to its slippery... we go there sir... ahhm so that we can finish our research on time...)

But despite of these experiences that sometimes puts their safety at risk they remain strong and steadfast with there goals. These risks help them mold and developed their resilience, ability and motivation towards research. The participants showed that despite of the difficult experiences they have encountered due to their remote locations that sometimes put their safety at risk they are still eager and motivated to understand the process of research. And will excel and master research in the future.

...pero bisan pa nano pa iton nga mga sitwasyon nga delikado... amon iton siya atubangon... kay para madevelop an amon kaugalingon nga character... ngan para mahibaro kami san tama nga proseso san paghimo research... ngan ahmm para magdati kami sana sa future ngan para makaya namon makipagsabayan san mga studyante na adto sa proper ...

(...but whatever dangerous situations we encountered... we will face it...so that we can developed our own self and character... and in order to learn the entire process of writing and conducting research... and ahmm in order for us to become knowledgeable about research in the future and for us to keep up with students living in the city proper.)

4.2 Challenges encountered by SHS students in remote and disadvantage areas

Conducting research poses a significant challenge for students, especially to those students in remote and disadvantage areas requiring considerable time, resources and effort to complete (Odena & Burgess, 2017). Given this demanding task, it is crucial to explore the lived experiences of SHS students living in remote and disadvantaged areas as they write and conduct their research as part of their SHS curriculum. The following themes were emerge from the responses of the participants; (1) Socioeconomic factors; (2) Access to Educational Resources, Technology and Opportunities; (3) Safety, health and well-being; (4) Lack of engagement and motivation.

4.2.1 Theme 1: Socioeconomic factors.

Majority of the participants agreed during the interview and FGD sessions that socioeconomic factors is one of the challenges they encountered as they write and conduct their research. Given the fact that they are located in remote and disadvantageous areas of Calbayog City, financial constraints were collectively one of the many factors that challenge students along the way as they write and conduct research.

“challenge financially sir...kay... ahmmm... permi kami mayda problema sir na konektado sa kwarta... parehas sir san minsan diri kami makapadayon san amon grupo paghimo san amon research... tungod kay wara kami kwarta sir para ipalit namon sin load san cellphone sir.”

(financial challenge sir... since ... ahm.. we always have a problem sir that is financially connected... like sometime... our group can't continue to our research... since we do not have money to buy load sir...)

“Minsan sir diri kami nakakakadto sa Calbayog para dumulhog ngan mahimo an mga importante na mga bagay san amon research sir kay wara kami kwarta igparasahe san habal-habal.”

(Sometimes we can't go to Calbayog City to do some important things with our research sir because we don't have money for the fair of habal-habal.)

“An amon grupo sir kay financially challenge... kay diri kami nakakadali-dali paggawas san kwarta tungod kay an amon papa ngan mama waray sira extra income.”

(Financially challenge amon grupo sir... because we can't immediately produce money since our parents do not have other extra income.)

While socioeconomic factors can create barriers to educational opportunities and resources (Moses & Muhammad, 2019). Families with lower socioeconomic status may struggle to provide basic necessities, let alone educational materials and technological devices that are essential for learning. This lack of resources can hinder the participant's ability to fully engage with the research process. And achieve their academic potential.

Another factor that posed challenge is the education level of every inhabitant in their area which also appeared under socioeconomic factor. The participants agreed that another challenge is the educational attainment of the people in that area. Since almost all of them were not a graduate of high school it seems that no one can help them with their research aside from their teachers.

“An kuan liwat sir an mga tawo didi kay diri graduate sa high school... tungod kay diri sira mga propesyunal... na fefeel namon na nahahadlok sira na mag kuan sa amon... ngan ahmm... mayda kami problem san pagpamiling san amon respondents kay kasagaran diri mag-aram bumasa ngan umintindi sir san mga letra.”

(As well as the people sir who were not a graduate... since they are not professional... we feel that they are afraid to engage with us... and ahmm... and we are having a problem in finding for the respondents since almost of them do not know how to read and understands words.)

This can influence the home environment and the support students receive from their families. Parents with lower socioeconomic status may have limited access to quality education themselves, which can impact their ability to support their children's learning. Additionally, parents with lower socioeconomic status may face challenges in being involved

in their children's education due to time constraints, work demands, or limited education on how to support their children's learning.

Moreover, according to Ankit, Ankit & Ankit (2016) socioeconomic factors can also affect students' psychological well-being. Students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds may experience stress and anxiety related to financial insecurity, which can negatively impact their academic performance. Additionally, these students may face social and emotional challenges related to their socioeconomic status, such as feelings of inferiority or isolation, which can further hinder their academic progress.

"Tungod kay wara kami kwarta sir... ahmm... diri danay namon napapadayon an amon pag search sa internet kay wara kami pan load... Diri namon napapadayon an paghimo san amon research ngan... kay ako man an ira leader... permi ak nakaka feel sir nerbyos ngan stress parapinsar san mga posibilidad nga... ahmm pano kun diri namon mahuman an amon research sa tama na oras... diri ak mapakali sir kun an amon internet load ma expired na."

(Since we don't have that financial stability sir... ahmm... when we do not have money to buy load for our internet... We can't continue with our research sir and... as there leader... I felt nervous and stress thinking of the possibilities that... ahmm what if we can't finish our research on time... I am not at ease everytime our internet expired.)

4.2.2 Theme 2: Access to Educational Resources, Technology and Opportunities.

Lack of educational resources such as school libraries, laboratories, textbooks, technologies such as computers, printers as well as educational opportunities that could improve once knowledge about research were the main cry of the participants. It is evident in the interview and FGD sessions that the participants were hoping that someday they will be given some educational resources especially textbooks that could help them improved their knowledge not just only in writing and conducting research but their knowledge as a whole.

"Sa ungod la sir, an pagconduct namon research is diri makuri, an pinaka rason la kay nano nakaka experiences kami sini na mga kakurian kay tungod san amon lokasyon... ngan wara lat kami mga access san mga resources."

(To be honest sir, conducting the research sir is not that difficult, the very reason why we somewhat experiences challenges is due to our location... since we do not have an immediate access to resources.)

"Ahmm... an kakurina na amon na encountered san amon grupo san paghimo namon yana research is una... ahmm... an kakulangan san mga educational resources sumala san books. Kay permi la kami naasa sir san load ngan internet pamiling mga impormasyon."

(Ahmm... the challenges that we encountered with my groupmates as we are doing our research is number 1... ahm.. the lack of resources... like books. Everytime we find for information we always rely on the internet...)

"Ahm kuan... I mean an usa namon na challenge sa pagkuha san impormasyon na related san amon research topic sir... like sa ahmmm Review of Related Literature and Studies... kuan na challenge kami kun iisipon kay wara didi permanente na internet connectivity ngan wara damo na mga libro... so asya an amon challenge."

(ahm yung... I mean the one in terms of obtaining some information sir... like ahmmm for our Review of Related Literature and Studies.... Ahmm kuan we are challenge by it because considering that we do not have stable internet connectivity and enough books.... So we are challenge by this one.)

Another challenge encountered by these students were in terms of technology. Due to their strategic geographical locations and socioeconomic factors almost majority of the participants do not have technological resources like computers, printers and even cellphones to be used for searching.

"Usa pa na challenge sir... is an teknolohiya. Suma san laptops, printers or bisan cellphones nala sir... kay asya gud an pinaka kailangan namon san amon paghimo research."

(Another sir... is the technology. Like laptops, printers or even cellphones... that is very needed in making our manuscript...)

"Sir... tungod kay ahmm wara didi available printers. An usa na available printer sa amon skwelahan kay wara liwat inks. Mao... ahm gin sabot nala namon amon teacher na ig extend and deadline san submission."

(Sir... since ahm there is no available printers. And the printer in our school has no available inks. So... ahm we asked our teacher to extend the deadline.)

In line also with challenge in technology, it is also evident in the interview that the participants are having challenge in terms of electricity. Which is one of the major components and needs of the participants when it comes to writing and conducting research. Since if their area will experience power outages for longer hours, they can't charge their cellphones and they can't access the internet.

"Usa pa liwat na challenge sir... kay an kuryente tungod... minsan nakaka experience kami didi halagba na oras san brownout na nakaka undang ngan nakaka apekto san amon oras ngan schedule paghimo san amon research... tungod ahmm amon mga battery san cellphones kay lowbat ngan diri ma charge."

(Another challenge sir... is the electricity because... sometimes we experience here longer blackouts which hinder and affect our time schedule for our research sir... since ahm our cellphones battery is dead.)

"Usa sir pa liwat is an kuryente... permi kami nakaka experience brownout didi tungod san durudilain nga mga rason...tapos kun wara kuryente sir labi na sa gabe... diri kami nakakapadayon san amon research...labi na sa pagsurat ngan maghimo san research manuscript tungod kay masirom... tapos amon nala ig tipid ini...)

(Another sir is the electricity... we always experience power outages due to various reasons... and if there is no electricity especially at night, we... can't make our research sir... especially our manuscript writing... since it is dark... and we will save our lamp gas...)

Furthermore, aside from the challenge in electricity, the participants also encounter unstable internet connectivity. This challenge allows participants to doubled their exerted efforts just to have a stable internet connection.

"An rason kay nano nakaka experience kami danay sir kakaiba ngan extra ordinary na experience kay tungod san maluya na internet sir."

(The reason why we experience those extra ordinary and unique experience that we have sir is due to poor internet connectivity.)

These lack of access to resources, technology and opportunities can hinder their ability to fully engage with the curriculum and achieve their academic potential (Reddy, 2015). This can further create a significant barrier to learning, particularly in today's digital age. Students in remote and disadvantaged areas may not have access to computers, the internet, or other digital tools, which can limit their ability to complete assignments, access online learning resources, and collaborate with their peers.

4.2.3 Theme 3: Safety, health and well-being

It is evident among the participants that they always faced and encounter challenges that could affect their safety, health and well-being. According to Matin and Khan (2017), everyone cannot avoid some situation that can posed there safety at risk, affect their health and state of well-being when conducting research.

"Usa ka adlaw sir... ahm habang nabaktas kami tikang san igbaw san buntay... naka tupo namon an usa ka grupo san mga Pulang Araw sir... hadlok gudman namon sadto na oras sir tungod... nga kami diri namon aram an amon hihimoon ngan kun nano an ira hihimoon sa amon... amon nala ginhimo is umagi nala kami sa ira na mamingaw... ngan naka tungok amon mga ulo bawal manutok..."

(one time sir... ahm while we are walking from the hill... we bumped into an armed groups sir... we are very afraid at that time sir since... we don't know what they will do to us... what we did it we passed them quietly while... we nod our heads...)

"Akon liwat challenges sir is kuan... Madali laak ma stress yana ngan mag problema... kun diri ko mahuman dayon an gin assign sa akon san amon leader na parts san manuscript... umabot ngani adto san time sir nga ginharomohom ak kay nauranan ak sir... kay kuan gin pirit ko na mahuman an kanan Research design namon..."

(I have these challenge sir which is... I get stress easily sir if I won't finished those parts that was given to me by our leader... one time it reaches to a point that I got sick due to heavy rain... since I force myself to finish the Research Design which was assigned to me...)

This was also agreed by Wegener, Meier and Ingerslev (2016) that both states that those students who are conducting research will reach to a point along the process that they will be bombarded with different challenges that could affect their health, state of well-being and sometime their safety. They also added that those students who are in far flung areas seems to suffer greatly from these challenges because they will exert double efforts and overcome other factors that could add to this challenge.

4.2.4 Theme 4: Lack of Engagement and Motivation

Lack of Engagement and Motivation is one of the challenge encountered by the SHS students living in remote and disadvantage areas that was evident in the one-on-one, face-to-face interview. These lack of engagement among members and among individuals in their barangay posed challenges to them. That could sometimes lead to burnout, stress and demotivation among the participants. According to Hay and Samra-Fredericks (2016), disengaged and unmotivated students are less likely to invest the necessary time and effort into their research projects. This often results in superficial or incomplete research, lacking depth, critical analysis, and innovation.

“...ngan ahmmm an iba kay wara interest san paghimo san research sir... tungod kay ahmmm... an ira isip kay an paghimo research is usa liwat na responsibilidad na ira ig consider... tapos an paghimo kuno research is diri makabulig sa ira... diri man kuno sira mapapakaon san research sa usa ka adlaw.”

(and ahmmm others also has no interest in doing our research... because ahmm... there mindset is that doing research comes into another responsibility... and doing research will not help them... eat a meal for the day.)

“Ahmmm mga wara sira interest sa research sir... gintutuyo gud nira na diri bumulig sir sa amon research... tungod kay... ahmm nano man kuno an ira makukuha sana na research? Mapapakaon ba kuno sira san research sa usa ka adlaw? Makakabulig ba an research san ira kapobrehan?... asya an ira mga paminsar.”

(ahmm they do not have interest with research... they tend not to help in our research sir... because their reason is... ahmm what they will gain in research? Do research feed them in a day? Do research help them ease poverty? ... that's their mindset sir.)

Further, lack of motivation can lead to procrastination and abandonment of research projects. Students may start a project with initial enthusiasm but fail to complete it due to waning interest and engagement. As mentioned also by Al-Qaderi (2016), Poor engagement in research can lead to lower grades, which can affect students' academic records and future educational opportunities.

“...Opo sir... kay an amon mga classmates ngan ka grupo is waray pakialam sir. Kaya an result wara naman nahuman amon research proposal. Ngan wara kami naka proceed lugod sa amon defense. Ngan an amon grade lugod sir san Midterm is kagutiay. Gutiyay nala na mabagsak ak sir”

(...yes sir... because some of our classmates and group members seems to be nonchalant. And the result is we didn't finished our research proposal. That is why we didn't proceed to our defense. With that our grades in Midterm is very low. I am actually at the edge of failing.)

Aside from unmotivated group members, the participants also feel that the people in their community seems to be unsupported. They don't want to engage and act as a respondents or participants of the study. As a result, the researcher seems to have difficulty in finding and searching for participants.

“Usa pa na challenge na amon na encounter sir kay an diri pakipag cooperate san mga tawo dinhi sa among barangay sir... nadiri sir ana magin respondents or participants san amon ginhihimo na research study... mao an resulta makadto kami sa iba na barangay or sa Calbayog para makabiling la mga respondents or participants.”

(Another challenge that we encounter sir is lack of cooperation among the people here in our barangay sir... they do not want to be a respondents or participants of the study... as a result we tend to go to other barangay or to the city proper to find for a respondents and participants.)

As a result, consistent disengagement can lead to a cycle of failure and low self-esteem. Students may begin to doubt their capabilities, which can affect their confidence in undertaking future academic or personal challenges (Adamek, 2015).

4.3 Differences in terms of Experiences and Challenges between SHS students in accessible and urban areas and SHS students in remote and disadvantaged areas

Living between an area that is accessible and urbanize seems to have a bigger difference in terms of many aspects. One of this aspect is in terms of education and opportunities. According to Mirasol and Inovejas (2017), students in accessible and urbanize area will have a greater opportunity with it comes to education as compared to students who were living in remote areas. As resulted from the one-on-one, face-to-face interview and FGD sessions conducted from the participants, two themes emerge. These are (1) Differences in terms of educational opportunities and resources; (2) Interest and knowledge.

4.3.1 Theme 1 Differences in terms of educational opportunities and resources

Majority of the participants mentioned that there is a greater difference between them and the students who were living in accessible and urbanized areas in terms of access to different educational resources such books and computers as well as to different educational opportunities that could help them in conducting and writing a research study. According to them, those SHS students living in accessible and urbanized areas is privilege to have an immediate access to educational resource that are also free. They also highlighted that these students were blessed since there encountered challenges and daily experiences as they conduct and write their research study is not that hard and difficult. Unlike them, that they reach to a point that they will face situations and challenges that could sometimes affect their health and well-being as well as their safety.

“Kuan sir... ahmm siguro damo pagkakaiba an mga SHS na mga studyante na adto sa Calbayog proper ngan kami sir. Kay kun imo sira obserbahan sir malaksi sir makahimo san ira research manuscript ngan malaksi sira maka conduct san ira mga research activities parehas san pagpa answer san ira mga questionnaire. Kami didi sir... ahmm kaloy’an sa Diyos swertehay na kun makabiling kami signal na diri nawawara-wara. Sa ira kasi sir ada na dayon tanan... ahmm ada na dayon an signal, an laptop ngan mayda pa gud mga haragni la na mga libraries. Ngan an ira sir skwelahan na iba mayda pa gud mga library... diri parehas sa amon na need pa namon magsinakasaka ngan magbyahe byahe.”

(I mean sir... ahmm maybe there are lots of difference between the SHS students living in Calbayog proper and to our sir. Because if you will be going to observe them, they can immediately make and finish their research and they can easily conduct different research activities that were related to their research like distributing their survey questionnaire. Unlike us here sir... ahmm it's a pure luck if we can find for a very stable and strong internet signal. To them sir it is already given... ahmm like the stable internet connection, computers and laptops and readily available and accessible libraries. And some of their schools has its own libraries unlike here that we need first to find for stable internet and travel long hours until we can get information.)

“Para sa akon kadako san pagkakaiba sir. Ahmm... usa na sir nga pagkakaiba is an mga tawo sir. Kay an mga tawo didto sir pwede nira dayon maaaruan bulig kun need nira mga explanation kay nagpa katapos an kasagaraan didto. Mga graduate sa college sir. Unlike didi sa amon barangay sir na tuman la nakakatungtung san skwelahan. Usa pa sir na pagkaka iba is an mga educational resources. Mayda na dayon sira mga gagamiton like a laptop kay magyaman ngan mayda mga mag-upay na trabaho an ira mga kag-anak.”

(For me sir there is actually a big difference. Ahmm... one difference sir is the people. Because the people there is knowledgeable and can easily be tapped for help by them since almost all of them where professionals and is graduate on college. Unlike here in our place, that most of the people where not graduate and they didn't finish their studies. Majority of them were elementary and high school graduate only. Another difference sir is the difference in terms of educational resources. Since they already have laptops and computers because their parents where has a good work and extra income.)

4.3.2 Theme 2: Interest and knowledge

Majority of the participants agreed that the knowledge and interest of the SHS students living in accessible and urbanized areas is different from the SHS students who live in remote and disadvantage areas. They highlighted that those SHS students in accessible areas seems to be interested and is knowledgeable in writing and conducting research. On the other hand, it is agreed by the participants that not all of SHS students living in remote and disadvantage areas were interested in writing and conducting research. In fact, these uninterested participants were one of the problems and a challenge being faced by other SHS students since it affects them.

“Sir usa pa liwat na pagkakaiba sir is an interest san mga ka grupo namon sir. Kay an iba san amon classmates na nag coconduct research is diri mga interesado. An ira mindset is iba sir. Nanohon man kuno nira iton na research na diri man iton makakabulig sa ira nga makakaon sa usa kaadlaw.”

(Sir another difference sir is the interest of our groupmates. Because some of our classmates were uninterested. There mindset where different from us. They always reason out that what will they do to that research if research will not help them eat for a day.)

Aside from interest, another difference agreed upon by the majority of the participants during the conducted one-on-one, face-to-face interview is about the knowledge they have. According to them, those SHS students in accessible areas seems to be knowledgeable and equipped with basic knowledge about research. Its technicalities and about the tedious process it may have. Unlike those SHS students in remote and disadvantaged areas that sometimes they lack basic knowledge in research processes and would result to failure and discontinuation of the research study. Further, there lack of the basic knowledge would somehow lead them to unstable mental health, stress and anxiety.

“An pagkakaiba siguro sir kay an amon knowledge pati understanding kun panino gud ba an paghimo san research. Akon na oobserbahan sir an anak san akon aunte na adto yana naistar sa Calbayog ngan na iskwela sa City high, kadati nira maghimo sir research... ahmm kadali la nira mahuman ngan kag-upay pa gud san ira tittle ahmm... diri parehas sa amon nga maiha maghimo labi na an paghimo namon san manuscript namon... hahaha... ahmm kakuri sir mag English gud. Naabutan kami tag pira ka oras.

(Maybe the difference between us and those living in Calbayog proper and other accessible area would be in terms of knowledge sir. As I observe the daughter of my aunt who is living in Calbayog proper and currently studying in City High, she is very intelligent and knowledgeable in making their research... she can easily finished every parts of the manuscript and there research study is very good... ahmm unlike ours that we are so slow in making research especially in making the research manuscript parts where we spent lots of time in making it since ahmm... we are having hard time writing it because it is English.)

But despite of this struggles and big differences, the participants still believe that they can still keep up with them since their experiences and challenges makes them more motivated to learn and turned them into a more resilient and stronger students; where they value there works and academic responsibilities. The participants further believe that despite of their locations and shortcomings in various things they can still rise and keep up with those in accessible area. They believe that they can still master how to write and conduct their research and excel in higher education and even in the field of works. And the participants were all hoping that time will come the government will provide them different educational resources and the support that they need not just in making and conducting research but also in other aspects of their study.

“...pero sir pasagdi la kun nagkukuri kami kay ini na amon mga kakurian pati mga na experience... siguro ahmm... natuod ak na hihimoon kami nga makusog ngan wise nga mga studyante. Tapos natuod na kaya lat namon makipagsabayan san mga SHS na studyante na adto sa mga accessible na mga lugar...”

(... but sir it's okey for us if we experience hardship because this challenges and experiences of ours... maybe ahmm... we believe that this will make us more wise and resilient students. We also believe that we can keep up with those SHS students who is residing in accessible areas.)

4.4 Strategies and coping approaches employed by SHS students in remote areas to overcome the challenges they had.

While students undeniably faced challenges in writing and conducting research, there were available means to overcome these difficulties. Their strategies and coping approaches enabled them to stay on track and finish their research study. Algorani and Gupta (2022) defined coping approaches as approaches to attitudes and actions utilized to deal with challenges and stresses brought on by a particular circumstance. Also, these coping approaches enable them to discover ways to keep going and get the task accomplished. Because of this, they allow themselves to focus all their energy and effort on schoolwork, mainly writing and conducting research, which leads them to finish successfully. With that the themes that emerge were; (1) Time management and Organization; and (2) Resourcefulness.

4.4.1 Theme 1: Time management and Organization

Majority of the participants often have limited access to research resources, including libraries, laboratories, and other academic facilities, which are more readily available in urban or affluent areas. Effective time management and organization can help them to optimize their use of the available resources, ensuring that they can conduct their research within the given time constraints.

"Iba pa sana sir... ahmm... magmamata kami san akon mga ka grupo kaagahan... ahm mga 3AM or 4Am... ngan ahmmm... makadto kami sa igbaw san buntay... ngan didto amon ubuson an oras tubtub 9AM pagpangusog search san mga impormasyon na kailangan san amon research ngan paghimo san amon research manuscript. Kay tungod amon gud gin mamanager amon oras kay maaram ka naman sir na didi sa amon lugar damo mga kakulangan san resources... so ig manage gud an oras."

(Aside from that sir... ahmm... we will try to wake up at the early dawn... ahm like 3AM or 4AM... and ahmm... we go to the mountain top sir... "Buntay" if they say... and spent the rest of the hour until 9 AM searching for information and writing our research manuscript. Because we are managing and organizing our time since we lack some of the resources due to our locations.)

Furthermore, the participants also responded during the FGD sessions that they often have to multitask, juggling their research works with other responsibilities such as household chores, caring for family members or other part time jobs like going to the field and do some works there. Time management and organization become crucial skills to help them balance these demands, ensuring that none of their tasks are neglected or overlooked.

"Kuan sir... naghihimo kami schedules did isa amon grupo... like 6 man kami san amon grupo ano... so an 3 na members sira la anay an mag himo san amon research... tapos an remaining 3 maghihimo san mga ira trabahoon na iba... tapos balyo naman sir... para gud ma sure na mahuman namon an amon research ngan an iba pa namon na hirimoon."

(kuan sir... we try to make schedules here in our group team... since we have 6 members in our group... we tend to divide it into 2... the first 3 members will be the one to do the research works... like searching for information... and the remaining 3 will do their other personal works... and vice versa... to make sure that our other works will not be overlooked.)

With this time management and organization can directly contribute to the academic success of SHS students in remote and disadvantaged areas. These skills can help them meet deadlines, maintain a steady pace of work, and ultimately produce high-quality research.

4.4.2 Theme 2: Resourcefulness

The participants often have limited access to research resources, including libraries, laboratories, and other academic facilities, which are more readily available in urban or affluent areas. Their resourcefulness can be demonstrated in their ability to locate and utilize alternative resource that they have.

"Tungod kay... mayda kami didi challenge sa technology... amon anay ginsusurat an mga impormasyon na amon nakuha sa internet. Ngan kun adto na kami sa skwelahan... naghuhuram kami sa laptop san amon teacher para ig encode an mga impormasyon na amon ginsurat... ngan nagamit kami liwat cellphone san pag encode sir.. tapos amon nala ini gintutuhay sa laptop."

(Since... we have here a challenge sir in terms of technology... we tend to write first those information that we have got from the internet.... And when we are at school... we tend to borrow the laptop of our teacher for us to encode... and we also tried to use our cellphones to encode sir.... Then we edit it in the laptop of our teacher.)

Further, the participants also sell different kinds of vegetables that are available in their garden just to earn enough money for the internet load or for habal-habal fare if they will go to City proper. This kind of resourcefulness skill of the participants is helpful to them in all aspects. Since it is the starting point for them to be creative in making solutions to the different future challenges in life.

"...kun wara kami kwarta igpa load sir... ahm... an amon grupo kay maglibot san mga garden san ira kada balay or sa bug'os na barangay ngan mamiling san mga bagay na pwede igbaligya... like an kuan mga prutas, kangkong or iba pa na mga gulay... kun swertehon kami sir... nga makakadamo kami prutas or gulay na igbabaligya namon... makakakuha kami durudako na kantidad san kwarta. Tapos an kwarta na amon nabenta sir... ahmm... gagamiton namon para magka mayda kami load pan search.

(...if we do not have money for our load... ahm... our group will go and roam around the vicinity of our barangay finding for something that we can sell... like fruits, kangkong, or any other vegetables... With that sir... if we got lucky...since we got many fruits or vegetables, we tend to get a big amount of money from selling. The money ahmm... that we got from selling sir... ahmm.. kuan we will use it sir to buy load.)

That is why, being resourceful in all aspects is very crucial skill every student must master along the way in making their research study. This reflects their ability to find creative solutions to the unique challenges they face, demonstrating their resilience, determination, and ingenuity in the face of adversity.

4.5 Impact their academic and personal growth.

Knowing the impacts of the different experiences and challenges encountered by the participants in their academic and personal growth we can adapt further strategies and lessen the effects of stress and burnout between them. With these the themes that emerge are (1) Expanded worldview; (2) Perseverance and Resilience; (3) Knowledge, Skills, Interest and Academic development.

4.5.1 Theme 1: Expanded worldview.

Majority of the participants responded in the one-on-one, face-to-face interview that their experiences and challenges encountered helps them broaden their perspective and understanding of the world. This often involves exploring diverse perspectives, cultures, and ways of life that may be different from the researcher's own experiences. Expanded worldview can help researchers to identify and challenge their own assumptions and biases, which is crucial in conducting ethical and respectful research (Mahammuda, 2016).

“An ini na mga challenges ngan experiences na may-ada ako is ginhimo ak niya na aware san durudilain nga mga aspeto san kinabuhi. Gin tagan ak niya higayon nga maintindihan an mga bagay-bagay na sobra pa san iya original na karuyag signgon.”

(This challenges and experiences I have make me aware with all the different aspects of life. It allows me to understand things in a way that is beyond its literal existence.)

It can also help researchers to build trust and rapport with participants, as they are able to understand and appreciate their unique experiences and worldviews.

“Gin buligan ak na ig improved an akon kaugalingon na para maintindihan an kinabuhi sa iba na pagkita.”

(This helps me improved my whole self, knowing the complexity of life in other perspective.)

4.5.2 Theme 2: Perseverance and Resilience.

Perseverance is the ability to continue working towards a goal despite of obstacles and setbacks. It is essential for overcoming the challenges they face in their research. On the other hand, resilience is the ability to bounce back from adversity and continue moving forward. Resilience is crucial for coping with the psychological and emotional challenges they may face during their research endeavour. These qualities enable them to overcome the challenges they face and persist in their pursuit of knowledge, despite the obstacles they encounter.

“Sure ako sir... tungod kay ini na mga challenges and experiences, nagin mas makusog ngan marig'on ako nga tawo. Ako an tawo nga diri Madali-dali na maapektuhan san mga maabot na problema.”

(I am sure sir, because with this challenge and experience, I became a strong and resilient person. Who didn't easily topple down by problems...)

“siguro... ini na mga experiences ngan challenges nakabulig sa akon para magin makusog ngan marig'on ako nga tawo sap ag-abot san panahon.”

(But... maybe our experiences and challenges help us become more resilient and strong individuals...)

“Ini siya ginhulma ngan gin ready kit sa aton kinabuhi... kay kun aadto na kit sa realidad san kinabuhi... waray na balikay pa...”

(This molded and ready us in life... because once you are in the field of life... there is no turning back...)

“Siguro sir... ini na mga challenges ngan experiences nakon gin hulma ak bilang usa ka tawo... ini na mga challenges and experiences ginhimo ak sini nga makusog ngan mabaskpog na tawo if ever diri ako makaeskwela diritso college.”

(I think sir... that challenges and experiences molded me as a person... that challenges and experiences make me a stronger person ready to conquer life if in case I can't go to college...)

Learning and mastering this kind of characteristics make the participants excel not just in making research but also in life as a whole. Building your resiliency will make you a better individual in the future. This can further exemplify that despite of the challenges and experiences the participants encountered as long as they have that resiliency in their heart and will persevere no matter what, they can be successful in the future.

4.5.3 Theme 3: Knowledge, Skill, Interest and Academic Improvement

The participants highlighted and strengthened their responses that their experiences and challenges in conducting and writing research has a big impact to them not just in terms of their knowledge, skills and academic improvement but also in their life as a whole. Majority of them agreed from conducted FGD session that those challenges encountered and experiences encountered helps them improved their grades not just only in one subject but also in their entire subject.

“Ahm kuan sir, basis an akon mga experiences ngan mga kakurian na naagian, siguro nakabulig ini sa akon para magin maupay an akon mga grado, diri la sa usa ka subject pero sa ngatanan.”

(Ahm kuan sir, with what I experienced and challenges faced, I think it helps me improved my grades and academic performance not just on these subject but also to outhet subject.)

“Opo Sir... ini na mga experiences ngan challenges nakon ngan akon mga ka grupo san paghimo san research kay mas nagin motivated kami sir nahumanon an amon research ngan paupayan ko akon pag-aaral)”

(Yes Sir... those experiences and challenges that we encountered along the process of making research make me motivated to finish my studies and improved myself in learning.)

These challenges and experienced turned them into a more responsible student. And it teaches theme lessons that can be useful for their life in general. These help theme balance their life.

5 Conclusion

The identified live experiences of the SHS students living in remote and disadvantaged areas of Calbayog City as they write and conduct their research study as part of their SHS curriculum demonstrate a high degree of resilience and perseverance. This is due to their transformative, interpersonal, and varied everyday experiences. The findings confirm the study of Kuper and Huges (2014) as cited by Dziuban et. al. (2020) that states that students in remote and inaccessible areas seems to have a varied and transformative experiences as compared to students in accessible areas. This further concluded that students in remote and inaccessible areas may develop a different perspective on learning, problem-solving, and life in general. That would lead them to master the process of writing and conducting a research study. These students are likely to exhibit resilience, adaptability, and creativity in overcoming the obstacles posed by their environment, leading to a transformative educational experience. Which was strengthened by Thompson and Palmer (2022) that revealed that students in accessible areas may have easier access to educational resources, technology, and opportunities. While this can be advantageous in many ways, it may also limit their exposure to diverse perspectives and challenges that students in remote areas encounter. As a result, their educational experiences may be more standardized and less transformative as compared to their counterparts in remote areas.

Moreover, although these SHS students in remote and disadvantaged areas lack interest and motivation but it doesn't mean that they will not keep up with those SHS students in accessible areas in terms of making research and excel or master the basic skills in writing and conducting research, because there unique experience alone and challenges encountered will mold and helped them developed their own unique characteristics that would helped them expand their worldviews to all the things around them. Also, with the different challenges faced by these students, they tend to develop a much more unique strategies and coping approaches that would help them fight stress, anxiety and even depression that is being brought by the tedious process of research as well as the lack of educational resources and opportunities. In addition, the students' coping mechanisms in writing research gave them the strength to be more productive despite the difficulties encountered. Necessary intervention paved the way for the education stakeholders to continue motivating the students and add some strategies to write research effectively and efficiently to achieve academic success.

Meanwhile, the study also concluded that in order to lessen those situations that could put the safety of the students at risk the government should provide and give different educational resources such as textbooks, small school libraries and even improved technological capabilities of the country. So that this will reach those areas that are being hindered by their geographical locations. And would help these students to be knowledgeable in research and would give solutions to the existing phenomena that those students in remote areas lack knowledge about research.

In general, the lived experiences of these SHS students living in remote and disadvantaged areas helped everyone about the situations of these students as they make and create their research study.

Recommendations

In the context of this study, wherein the researcher delved into the lived experiences of SHS students living in remote and disadvantaged areas as they conduct their research study as part of their SHS curriculum, several recommendations emerged that hold the potential to fortify and sustain this within the framework. The following suggestions are put forth

- **Support Resilience and Perseverance:** Acknowledge and celebrate the resilience and perseverance demonstrated by SHS students in remote and disadvantaged areas. Implement programs or initiatives that nurture these qualities and provide support systems to help students overcome challenges and obstacles.
- **Enhance Access to Educational Resources:** Advocate for increased access to educational resources, technology, and learning materials for students in remote and disadvantaged areas. Collaborate with government agencies, NGOs, and private sector partners to bridge the digital divide and ensure equitable access to quality education.
- **Diversify Perspectives:** Create opportunities for students in both remote and accessible areas to interact, collaborate, and exchange ideas. Organize cultural exchanges, virtual learning sessions, and collaborative projects to expose students to diverse perspectives and experiences.
- **Government Intervention:** Advocate for government intervention to improve educational infrastructure and resources in remote areas. Lobby for the provision of textbooks, school libraries, and technological capabilities to enhance the learning environment and ensure equal educational opportunities for all students.
- **Continuous Motivation and Support:** Sustain motivation and support for SHS students in remote and disadvantaged areas by engaging education stakeholders, teachers, parents, and community leaders. Implement strategies to boost student morale, recognize achievements, and provide ongoing guidance and mentorship.
- **Safety Measures:** Prioritize student safety by addressing environmental risks and ensuring secure learning environments. Collaborate with local authorities and educational institutions to implement safety protocols, emergency response plans, and infrastructure improvements to safeguard the well-being of students.
- **Policy Advocacy:** Advocate for policy changes at the local, regional, and national levels to address systemic barriers that hinder educational equity for students in remote areas. Collaborate with policymakers, advocacy groups, and education stakeholders to raise awareness of the challenges faced by these students and advocate for policy reforms.
- **Curriculum Adaptations:** Review and adapt the curriculum to reflect the diverse experiences and contexts of students in remote and disadvantaged areas. Incorporate local knowledge, cultural perspectives, and real-world examples into the curriculum to make learning more relevant and engaging for these students.
- **Sustainability and Long-Term Planning:** Ensure that educational policies and practices aimed at supporting students in remote and disadvantaged areas are sustainable and part of long-term planning efforts. Invest in infrastructure, capacity-building, and community partnerships to create lasting impact and empower students to succeed in their educational journey.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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